

Studies on effect of silane coupling agent on the mechanical properties of clay filled natural rubber

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Effect of treatment of coupling agents bis(3-triethoxysilylpropyl)tetrasulphide (Si-69) on mechanical properties of composites made from natural rubber and clay is reported here. The treatment resulted in enhancement of mechanical properties of composites of the said rubber when compared with untreated clay composites separately. The properties under consideration were tensile strength, modulus at 100% and 400%, Young's modulus, elongation at break, hardness, etc. Tensile strength was improved by 118.75%, modulus at 400% was found to improve by 422% while Young's modulus also was improved by 133% when compared with untreated clay composites at 0.42 volume fraction.

Coupling agents are molecular bridges at the interface between two dissimilar substrates, such as an inorganic/organic filler, fiber or pigment and an organic polymer matrix. When used in filled polymers, they improve impact strength, exhibit melt viscosity lower than that of virgin polymer at inorganic loadings above 50 per cent, and enhance maintenance of mechanical properties during aging. Coupling agents form monomolecular layers on the substrate of most materials. In this work the effect of silane coupling agent on mechanical properties of composites made from natural rubber and clay (treated and untreated) has been studied. One coupling agent silane was selected for the treatment of filler clay separately. One gram of coupling agent is treated with 100 g of clay and then the composites of chloroprene rubber filled with treated and untreated clay are prepared with various filler loadings and their properties are compared in this work. Tensile strength was improved by 118.75%, modulus at 400% was found to improve by 422% while Young's modulus also was improved by 133% when compared with untreated clay composites at 0.42 volume fraction.

Experimental

Materials : Bis(3-triethoxysilylpropyl)tetrasulphide (Si-69) was imported from (DEGUSSA-HULS) West Germany, china clay was procured from local supplier. The rubber manufactured by Denki Kogaku Kogyo Ka bushiki Kalsha, Japan was used in the present work, other chemicals (such as a stearic acid, zinc oxide, antioxidant, accelerator (I), accelerator (II), sulphur), used were manufactured

by Bayer India Ltd. Physical parameters of chloroprene rubber, silane coupling agents and constituents of clay are reported as below :

Physical characterization of silane coupling agents (Si-69) : Chemical name – Bis(triethoxysilyl)propyltetrasulphide; purity – 95%; mol. wt. – 639.06; sp. gr. – 1.07; refractive index – 1.074; flash point – 91°C; b.p. – 250°C; density (g/cm) – 1.0850; viscosity – 11–12 cp; pH – 7–9.

Constituents of China clay : SiO₂ – 46.29; Al₂O₃ – 38.38; Fe₂O₃ – 0.30; TiO₂ – 0.02; CaO – 0.161; MgO – 0.59; Na₂O – 0.15; K₂O – 0.15; ignition loss at 100°C – 13.59.

General characteristics of natural rubber : Appearance – brown; polymer system - emulsion: sp. gr. – 0.98; ash content – 0.20%; pH – 5.05–4.77.

Particle size analysis :

Surface area is a major parameter in connection with filler-matrix interaction for reinforcing purposes. The finer the particle size, the higher is the surface area and higher the reinforcement. The details regarding particle size distribution of the clay used in the study are given in Fig. 1. The figure clearly indicates that about 60% particles had diameter 2 µm or less. While 90% of the filler had particle diameter of 6 µm. The analysis was done on Shimadzu SALD-2001 instrument by a Shimadzu (Asia Pacific) Pvt. Ltd., Singapore.

Fig. 1. Graph of particle size distribution of clay.

Treatment on clay by silane coupling agent :

The coupling agent (1 g) was mixed³⁻¹⁴ with ethylalcohol (100 ml) to make a solution for applying to filler (100 g) separately. 100 g clay was mixed in 100 mL solution of coupling agent i.e. 1 g of the coupling agent (silane) was used per 100 g of filler clay. The solution was stirred for 30 min to ensure uniform distribution. The treated filler (clay) was then dried at 100°C in an oven for about 5 h to allow complete evaporation of the alcohol.

Fig. 2. Tensile strength as a function of treated and untreated clay - NR composites.

Preparation of composites :

The compounding of the rubber was carried out on laboratory scale two roll mill. The rubber was first masticated for 5 min. Additives were added as : Rubber (NR) - 100; stearic acid - 3.0; zinc oxide - 3.0; vulconex [antioxidant : *N*-(1,3-dimethyl butyl)-*N*-phenyl-*p*-phenylene diamine] - 1.0; TMT [accelerator (I) : tetramethyl thiuram disulphide

Fig. 3. Modulus at 100% elongation as a function of treated and untreated clay - NR composites.

(TMTD)] - 0.5; ZDC [accelerator (II) : zinc diethyl dithiocarbamate (ZDC)] - 0.5; sulphur - 3.0; fillers (treated and untreated) - variable (10-100); curing time - 30 min; curing temp. - 145°C. After the addition of all of the additives, the compounding was continued for 30 min for homogeneous mixing. The curing characteristics were determined using a multichannel DTA. The curing time was determined by subjecting compounds to DTA at 150°C, for various intervals and observing the thermograms^{4,10}.

Fig. 4. Elongation at break (%) as a function of treated and untreated clay - NR composites.

This compounded matter was then vulcanized using sulfur system by press curing method (compression molding machine) at 150°C for 30 min in chrome plated mould having cavity dimensions (15 cm × 15 cm × 0.3 cm).

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) :

SEM was carried out by Leica Cambridge (Stereoscan

Alkadasi *et al.* : Studies on effect of silane coupling agent on the mechanical properties of clay filled natural rubber (440) scanning electron microscope (Cambridge, UK) Polymer specimens were coated with gold (50 μm thick) in an automatic sputter coater (Polaron Equipment Ltd., Scanning electron microscope coating unit E5000, UK). Acceleration potential was 20 kV. Photographs of representative areas of the sample were taken at 1000X magnifications.

Plate 1. SEM of untreated clay filled - NR at volume fraction (0.44)

Measurement of mechanical properties :

Mechanical properties such as tensile strength, modulus at 100%, 400% were determined by subjecting dumbbell shaped specimens (in confirmation with ASTM D-412) to a universal testing machine (R & D Equipment, Mumbai, India). The sheets from which specimens were cut had been conditioned for 24 h prior to subjecting to universal testing machine (100 kg load cell), at a crosshead speed of 50 cm/min. Hardness was measured on Durometer (Blue-Steel, India) on shore - A scale.

Tensile strength .

It was observed that treatment resulted in increasing the capacity of the composites to accommodate more filler without deteriorating the properties. As expected the tensile strength of the composites filled with silane treated filler were higher than untreated. This increase was about 119% is shown in Fig. 2.

Modulus at 100% and 400% elongations :

The dependence of modulus at 100%, elongation with volume fraction of treated and untreated clay-NR composites is depicted in Fig. 3. It is seen that moduli increases initially, attains a maximum value for particular value of concentration of fillers and it decreases. The peak values of moduli of the composites lie at 0.45 volume fractions of clay treated and untreated. The modulus of treated clay is about 5.22 times higher than that of untreated clay. The initial rate of increment in the property with increasing volume fraction of the filler was similar in both the cases, however after volume fraction 0.30 the rate of increment for composites filled with treated clay was substantially high.

Elongation at break (%) .

The effectiveness of treatment was again found to be similar in the case of elongation at break too. Elongation at break for silane treated filler was about 980 as against the magnitude of 2000% for untreated filler. The results are graphically shown in Fig. 4

Plate 2. SEM of Si-69 treated clay filled - NR at volume fraction (0.50)

Young's modulus :

The treatment with 1.0% silane showed higher increase in Young's modulus as a result of untreated to clay filler.

Hardness :

It is seen that, hardness of the treated and untreated clay - NR composite linearly increases on increasing the concentrations of fillers, however hardness does not increase abruptly on increasing the concentration of untreated clay. As expected the hardness of composites increased with volume fraction of filler and with the treatment of filler.

SEM of composites :

SEM photomicrographs of composites of NR - clay are shown in Plates 1 and 2. It can be seen that the treatment of silane coupling agent influences the orientation of filler particles and is responsible for higher strength. Untreated composite fracture show non-adhesive appearance and formation of agglomerates while treated composites show a regular, adhesive appearance causing further enhancement.

Conclusions :

(1) Tensile strength of treated clay - NR composites show higher values compared to untreated one, showing the effect of silane coupling agent. The hardness of treated clay filled composites is slightly higher than untreated because of increased surface interactions.

In general polymer - filler interaction in presence of titanate coupling agent is enhanced.

(2) [Remark : Water also used with very small quantity of alcohol to reduce the cost].

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